

Exploring Tipping Points and Their
Impacts Using Earth System Models

Register of the Early Warning Indicators

Deliverable D4.1

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1. Abstract

This deliverable provides a synthesis of early warning indicators (EWIs) for major climate tipping elements, whose tipping risk is increasing under anthropogenic pressure. It combines approaches based on critical slowing down and understanding of physical processes to identify signals of impending abrupt transitions. The main contribution is the development of EWI registers for key systems (SPG, AMOC, Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets, and Arctic sea ice), compiling precursors, available and missing observations, threshold estimates, timescales, and indicator reliability. The analysis highlights significant observational gaps and uncertainties across many indicators, and offers recommendations to strengthen monitoring systems. Overall, this work establishes a structured foundation for developing operational early warning systems for climate tipping risks.

2. Work Done

Three online internal workshops were organised to agree on the content of the Early Warning Indicators (EWI) register. In addition, an in-person session involving the entire project team was held during the 2025 annual project meeting in Paris. These discussions brought together contributions from the project partners of WP4 and, more broadly, from all the TipESM people through a plenary discussion at the TipESM annual meeting. A specific collaboration was established with WP2 to integrate its key findings into the register. As a result, the register is grounded in expert elicitation within the project, supported by both existing literature and newly generated results. Further exchanges with external experts were conducted to strengthen the scientific consensus beyond the project consortium (e.g. TIPMIP-OCEAN community), notably including experts from the sister EU project ClimTIP.

3. Results Achieved: Registers of Early Warning Indicators for four tipping elements

3.1 Rationale for construction and description of the registers

Anthropogenic activities and emissions are placing increasing pressure on the climate system and its associated subsystems. Several of these subsystems are thought to exhibit strong non-linear behaviours

and may approach tipping points beyond which they undergo substantial—and potentially irreversible—changes (Lenton et al., 2008). These subsystems are referred to as *tipping elements*. Many are considered at risk of crossing their tipping points within this century (Armstrong McKay et al., 2022).

Before a tipping point is reached, some systems may display signs of growing instability. Among these are *early warning signals* (EWS), which are based on changes in the properties of system variability as a critical threshold is approached. Most classical EWS rely on the concept of *critical slowing down* (CSD), derived from dynamical systems theory. Other approaches aim to anticipate tipping risks through physical understanding and the identification of well-characterised thresholds beyond which a system may tip. These approaches define *early warning indicators* (EWIs) based on the evolution of precursor variables that tend to shift prior to tipping. In this work, we propose a synthesis of early warning indicators from the literature, including those developed within the TipESM project. This synthesis takes the form of an *EWI register*, organised into tables for a range of tipping elements. These include the North Atlantic subpolar gyre (SPG), the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets, the Amazon rainforest, and the Arctic sea ice. The assessment relies primarily on expert elicitation extending beyond the project team. Particular attention is given to evaluating observational datasets that enable monitoring of early warning indicators, identifying observational gaps, and providing guidance for future observation networks.

Each table includes the following information:

- Precursors, key processes, and associated early warning indicators,
- Observations for EWI: available datasets and those missing, and which are required for allowing the EWI to be correctly monitored (highlighted in **dark red colour**),
- Threshold estimates for precursor variables,
- Time scale of early warning,
- Reliability of CSD-based indicators,
- Sources of knowledge and supporting simulations.

The title of each table indicates the tipping element analysed. In addition, the lowest warming level at which the tipping point is crossed in some models, as well as the time length of the transition towards a new state following the crossing of the tipping point, are provided in parentheses. The acronym “n/a” means “not available” when no information on the topics seems to exist.

3.2 Register of early warning indicators (EWIs)

The register is available as a living document in open access in Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/20799814>

Updates to the register will be provided on the Zenodo document only. The tables below are reported here as a reference, but this deliverable will no longer be updated in this specific section.

SPG tipping element (<1.5°C, ~a decade)

Precursors, key processes and EWI	Observations for EWI: available, required	Threshold estimates for the precursor	Time scale of the early warning	CSD reliability	Source of knowledge, simulations available
Critical stratification in the SPG and associated threshold in sea surface salinity (SSS) in the SPG	SSS (hydrographic data: EN4, CORA remote sensing: SMOS, and salinity in the deeper layers (ARGO, reanalyses)	Critical salinity distance = 0.9 PSU (Almeida et al., in rev.)	~10 years	Poor (number of false positives)	CMIP5, CMIP6 CESM LENS large ensemble, TipESM_forced
Horizontal salt advection (positive feedback, Born & Stocker 2014), also from the North Atlantic drift deviation towards the Irminger and Labrador seas (Sgubin et al. 2017)	Barotropic streamfunction maximum (reanalyses, Sea Surface Height (SSH) from remote sensing altimetry) Estimate of salinity transport from the North Atlantic drift to the Irminger and Labrador Sea (reanalyses, Required: dedicated arrays west and east of the Irminger Sea) Estimate of salt transport by eddies in the Labrador Sea (Eddy Kinetic Energy from altimetry, SMOS)	Not estimated yet	n/a	n/a	

AMOC tipping element (<2°C, ~a century)

Precursors, key processes and EWI	Observations for EWI: available, required	Threshold estimates for the precursor	Time scale of the early warning	CSD reliability	Source of knowledge, simulations available
SPG and Nordic Seas convection (Drijfhout et al. 2025) and potential migration towards the Arctic (Lique et al. 2017)	Mixed Layer Depth estimate (reanalyses, Required: time series of estimates based on hydrographic data)	Collapse of mixed layer depth	~20 years	n/a	CMIP6
Build-up of fresh water in the Arctic	Required: More observations of salinity in the Arctic region. Continuous evaluation of the Fram Strait and the Canadian Archipelago freshwater transport (liquid and solid)	Arctic freshwater content and exports Collapse of Labrador Sea convection	~5-20 years	n/a	TipESM_forced simulation, CMIP6 NAhosMIP Transient 6K simulation from the project (IPSL)
Freshwater transport by the overturning at 34°S (van Westen et al. 2025)	Continue the SAMOC array on the Southern Ocean	Reversal of a trend	A few decades	n/a	RareEvent algorithm
Arctic overflows (Larsen et al. 2024)	Continue measurements across the Greenland Iceland Scotland ridge (Larsen 2024)	Collapse of the overflow	n/a	n/a	Estimates of observation from key processes (e.g. Fov)
Freshwater input from Greenland (Mehling 2026)	Reconstruction based on remote sensing data and regional		n/a	n/a	

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	atmospheric model (Bamber et al. 2020)	Not estimated yet			
Freshwater leakage from the SPG to the Canary current (Swingedouw et al. 2013)	SSS anomalies in the subtropical gyre from e.g. EN4 (SMOS is too short)	n/a	n/a	Not tested	
Value of the AMOC strength (Jackson et al. 2013)	OSNAP and RAPID	About 5-6 Sv at 26°N	A few years	Not working	

GIS tipping element (<4°C, ~a millennium)

Precursors, key processes and EWI	Observations for EWI: available, required	Threshold estimates for the precursor	Time scale of the early warning	CSD reliability	Source of knowledge, simulations available
Melt–elevation and surface Mass Balance (SMB) feedbacks; surface-melt early-warning indicators. Boers and Rypdal (2021) report a critical slowdown in central-western Greenland records using variance and lag-1 autocorrelation.	Ice-core melt records; EO/satellite products for ice melt duration, surface elevation, SMB, and mass change. Required: Linked melt/runoff, SMB, elevation-change, and mass balance observing chain.	Not established for a precursor variable. Armstrong McKay et al. (2022) provide a global-warming threshold of 1.5°C above pre-industrial, with a 0.8-3.0°C range. Bochow et al. (2023) provide overshoot threshold context, but not a local precursor threshold.	Not established in checked sources. Published ice-sheet transition timescales should not be used as early-warning lead times.	CSD/EWS reported for central-western Greenland, but not yet established for the whole ice sheet.	Boers and Rypdal (2021); Trusel et al. (2018); Armstrong McKay et al. (2022); Bochow et al. (2023); Robinson et al. (2012). Will complement with output analysis from TipMIP-ESM and CMIP7 simulations.
Surface-albedo decline and ice-albedo feedback as a monitored melt-amplifying process.	PROMICE/GEUS MODIS Greenland albedo daily grids. Required: Linked satellite, reanalysis, and regional climate model products for surface-albedo radiative forcing.	Not established in checked sources.	Not established in checked sources.	Not rated in checked sources	PROMICE/GEUS MODIS Greenland albedo dataset (see Refs.); Ryan et al. (2024) for surface-albedo feedback and melt amplification. Will complement with output analysis from

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					TipMIP-ESM and CMIP7 simulations.
Marine-terminating outlet-glacier and fjord dynamics.	PROMICE Sentinel-1 ice velocity mosaics; MEaSUREs NSIDC outlet-glacier velocity maps from optical; PROMICE/GEUS annual calving front lines. Required: named fjord/ocean forcing products.	Not established in checked sources.	Not established in checked sources.	Not rated in checked sources.	Solgaard et al. (2021) / PROMICE ice velocity; Howat (2016) NSIDC-0646 MEaSUREs selected glacier-site velocity maps; PROMICE/GEUS calving front line data sets.
Firn meltwater storage and retention affecting runoff timing; near-surface ice formation can limit storage and increase surface discharge.	Firn air-content observations and firn-compaction records, including western Greenland firn air-content compilation and FirnCover station data. Required: selected firn model or assimilation product for operational monitoring.	Not established in checked sources.	Not established in checked sources.	Not rated in checked sources.	Harper et al. (2012) for firn meltwater storage and retention; Machguth et al. (2016) for near-surface ice formation limiting storage; Vandecrux et al. (2019) for firn air content; MacFerrin et al. (2022) for FirnCover compaction data.

WAIS tipping element (<2°C, ~a few centuries)

Precursors, key processes and EWI	Observations for EWI: available, required	Threshold estimates for the precursor	Time scale of the early warning	CSD reliability	Source of knowledge, simulations available
Surface-driven collapse of ice shelves, driven by meltwater ponding and subsequent fracture	EO - of surface melt & ponding Velocity of ice shelves - inversion to stress regime Mapping of crevasses coupled to ice sheet modelling	unknown for major ice shelves	Years	n/a	Ocean water masses in front of the shelf (UKESM) - depth of thermocline Other ESMS, although, may need ice-shelf cavities (use knowledge of precursors from UKESM and apply to other ESM with cavities)
Large-scale basal melting of Ross ice shelf.		Widespread basal melting under the shelf, integrated > 200 Gt/yr.	Few decades	n/a	Meltponds - melt and depletion of firm reservoir - may need RCM output
Bottom temperature and salinity of the Ross ice shelf cavity water EWI metrics built from salinity and temperature at 500-800m in the continental shelf in the West Ross region (76.3-78S; 158-168W)	OCEAN ICE D1.1 (Shenjie et al., 2024) that covers 1972 - 2023 Required: ongoing measurements of salinity and temperature at depth in front of the ice shelf in the future	Volume-averaged bottom temperature of cavity water above the freezing point (-1.9°C). Volume-averaged salinity in the cavity below ~34.2 psu (est. by UKESM) For the metrics using depth range 500-800m in front of	Few decades	Testing	Crevassing in regions of the ice shelf that buttress the ice sheet Long enough simulations are not available with models in TipESM (e.g. Rosier et al. 2021)

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		the Ross ice shelf: threshold of temperature is 1°C while salinity is ~34.3psu (also from UKESM)			
Flux of ice across the grounding line of WAIS outlet glaciers. EWI is critical slowing, lag 1 autocorrelation, detrended fluctuation analysis, trend in variance	Continuous records of grounding line position. Ice sheet geometry and velocity. Likely on centennial timescales	Autocorrelation and Detrended Fluctuation metrics in Rosier et al., tending to 1	Decades to centuries	Probably low	

Sea ice tipping element (<2°C, ~a few decades)

Precursors, key processes and EWI	Observations for EWI: available, required	Threshold estimates for the precursor	Time scale of the early warning	CSD reliability	Source of knowledge, simulations available
Sea ice thickness thresholds (for September sea ice) (Dörr et al. submitted)	Ice thickness/volume observations	Sep ice volume < 4500 km ³ / mean Arctic ice thickness < 1.5 m.	Years to around 2 decades	n/a	TipESM-core TipESM-ensemble CMIP6 Large ensemble simulations
Ocean heat transport into the Arctic (for Sep sea ice) (e.g. Docquier et al. 2021; Auclair and Tremblay 2018))	Ocean heat transport (OHT) through the Barents Sea Opening (BSO)	OHT at BSO increases by > 50 TW	Years to 1 decade	n/a	
Snow melt date/ albedo/ melt pond fraction	Melt pond and albedo satellite observations	n/a	n/a	n/a	
Changes in Arctic Ocean temperature stratification	Ocean temperature in the Arctic and around the Antarctic. Required: better spatial and temporal sampling of temperature at depth	n/a	n/a	n/a	
Changes in atmospheric circulation patterns/ atm heat transports/ dynamical transports	Atmospheric circulation pattern changes	n/a	n/a	n/a	

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<p>Ocean heat transport through Barents Sea Opening (BSO) for winter sea ice in Barents Sea (Docquier et al. 2021)</p>	<p>OHT BSO</p>	<p>An increase of 10 TW BSO leads to a 30000-130000 km² winter ice area decline</p>	<p>1 year</p>	<p>n/a</p>	
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4. Open Access

The tables in section 3.2 will be published as a standalone document on Zenodo to enable versioning and a specific DOI attribution.

5. Contribution to the TipESM objectives

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project objectives.

SO4	To identify precursors of climate and ecological TPs, and develop reliable early warning indicators based on ESM models and observations. KPIs: A register of tipping points, early warning indicators and recommendations for future observational systems (Deliverables: D4.1 and D4.2).	Work packages: 1,4,5, and 6
<p>This deliverable D4.1 clearly contributes to the Objective SO4 outlined above. It provides a synthesis of early warning indicators (EWIs) identified within the project and those drawn from external sources. Furthermore, it situates these indicators in the context of their observability and offers recommendations for developing new observational systems. These recommendations aim to support the implementation of operational early warning systems based on the range of indicators presented in the deliverable.</p>		

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